

Pyrolysis-gasification of biomass using nickel modified catalysts: The effect of the catalyst regeneration on the product properties

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ABSTRACT

In this work, agricultural biomass waste (maize) was used as raw material in a pyrolysis-gasification process with the presence of nickel-loaded zeolites, CaO and Al₂O₃. Henceforward, the reusability and the deteriorating effect of the catalysts are important to be analysed, therefore the catalysts were reused for ten regeneration cycles. During the measurements, the effect of temperature, catalysts and the regeneration cycles of catalysts were also investigated, as well as the components of the gaseous product. At first, the proper temperature was determined in the 1st (200–800 °C) and the 2nd (500–700 °C) reactor zone, where 400 °C and 700 °C, while for the regeneration 800 °C was chosen. Throughout the regeneration cycles in case of Ni/ZSM-5 lighter hydrocarbons was increased while that of the carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide was decreased. In the presence of Ni/CaO the amount of carbon dioxide decreased until the 3rd regeneration cycle, while carbon monoxide and hydrogen was decreased till the 10th cycle. Regarding the Ni/Al₂O₃, the amount of CO₂ and CO was significantly decreased at each cycles, while in case of Ni/Clinoptilolite reduction was observed in hydrogen and carbon dioxide, however not only the amount of carbon monoxide but the syngas yield increased remarkably. Due to the mentioned results, the Ni/Clinoptilolite has an effective syngas enhancing and carbon dioxide capturing effect, even with low pyrolysis temperature.

1. Introduction

Biomass as a renewable energy source provides decreasing of the emitted CO₂ amount. Based on statics, globally, 170 billion metric tons of biomass source is available from which significant waste is left behind [1]. The products resulted in pyrolysis and gasification of different biomass can be used as an alternative fuel, blending component, besides its value-added conversation the products can reach the appropriate quality. In 2020, the emitted carbon dioxide was 31.5 Gt, which - based on the statics - will reach 37 Gt in 2023. It is important to note, that the predicted value can be reduced to 28.5–30 Gt by the use of sustainable and renewable materials [2–5].

The synthesis gas, sourced by biomass gasification is one of the most important intermediary components in the chemical industry. Based on the origin of the biomass, the gas product contain different

concentrations of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, methane, hydrocarbons with low molecular weight, sulphur, nitrogen and chlorine-containing compounds. Henceforward, purifying of the synthesis gas is an important issue, mainly for CO₂ capture [6–8].

During biomass pyrolysis-gasification, numerous reactions take place, therefore the composition of the gaseous product are mainly affected by them. E.g. the equilibrium reactions can be shifted to the appropriate composition with the use of steam and catalysts. Nickel-containing catalysts are commonly used owing to their high efficiency in cracking of the C–H, C–C and C–O bonds, their low price and their regeneration availability. Besides nickel, the ruthenium and the rhenium-containing catalysts can be listed, however, their price cannot be considered economic friendly, especially in scale-up. Regarding the catalyst support, the ZSM-5, HZSM-5, Al₂O₃, Al₂O₃–SiO₂ are the most commonly used. Henceforward, the CaO and the natural zeolites should be perspective materials, owing to their particle size and efficiency in

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Abbreviations

BET	Brunauer–Emmett–Teller
BJH	Barret–Joyner–Halenda
D_{av}	average pore diameter
FTIR	Fourier transform infrared
S_{BET}	specific surface area obtained by BET method
S_{micro}	specific surface area of micropores
TCD	Thermal conductivity detector
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
TPD	Temperature programmed desorption
V	pore volume
V_{micro}	Micropore volume

not only gasification processes, but in-situ carbon capture. Based on the literature, the CaO, as well as the natural zeolites, can be impregnated promoting the carbon capture processes and increasing the yield of the gaseous product [9–12].

Wang et al. investigated the effects of the Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/CaO during high-temperature biomass gasification [9]. They demonstrated, that the catalyst with CaO carrier can increased the gas yield, the hydrogen yield, however, decreased the amount of hydrocarbons with low molecular weight [9]. W.X. Peng et al. concluded, that the residue of high-temperature gasification of wood residue was significantly decreased in the presence of Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/Ce/Al₂O₃ catalysts, but higher gas yield was found using Ni/Ce/Al₂O₃ catalyst [13]. It is important to mention that the H₂/CO ratio was not significantly affected by the different amounts of the catalysts during the measurement [13]. Higher gas and hydrogen yield was also reported by Yue Chai et al. with the nickel content of Ni–CaO–C catalyst during biomass and plastic waste co-pyrolysis [14]. It is important to note that there was no significant change in the quality of the gaseous products over nickel content of 10%. Afterwards, the regenerated catalysts can be reused, but with decreased efficiency [15]. Shang et al. investigated the regeneration and cycle stability of Ni modified Zr-MOF catalyst during biomass gasification, where the agglomeration of nickel was indicated after several reuse. It was observed, that the catalytic performance of regenerated catalyst was slightly increased [16]. It was also concluded, that the zeolite catalysts had partially lost their activity due to several regeneration cycles using pinewood sample [17].

This work aims to investigate the pyrolysis-gasification of biomass with maximizing of the gaseous product and syngas, and simultaneously the carbon dioxide capture. The main goal of the experiments was to compare the effect of the CaO with zeolites in biomass gasification and CO₂ adsorption. Since the regeneration and the cycling reuse of the catalyst are proved to be a research gap, the efficiency of the catalysts during ten regeneration cycles was also investigated from an economic point of view.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw material

Crashed (<3 mm) and dried form of maize biomass waste (roots, leaves, stems, corn stalk) was used as raw material. Biomass sample has 36.5% carbon, 5.2% hydrogen, 0.9% nitrogen and 57.4% oxygen content.

2.2. Catalysts

During the experiments four different types of catalysts were used, namely are Ni/ZSM-5, Ni/Al₂O₃, Ni/CaO, Ni/Clinoptilolite. The support had been chosen based on their acidity, the efficiency in the cracking

reactions and the in-situ carbon capture effect in the relevant cases. The preparation method was the same in all cases. The catalyst supporters had been impregnated by the using of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O solution at 80 °C till 3 h, then the slurry was filtered and dried at 110 °C till 10 h. Finally the treated catalysts were calcined at 600 °C till 3 h.

The main surface properties of the catalysts were determined by a Micromeritics 3Flex 3500 instrument using the BET (Brunauer–Emmett–Teller) method. The pore-size distribution and pore volumes were calculated using the BJH (Barret–Joyner–Halenda) model. The temperature programmed desorption of ammonia (NH₃-TPD) was used to measure the number and acid strengths of sites found on solid catalysts using an analyser Micromeritics AutoChem-2920 precision chemisorption analyzer equipped with a heat-conductivity detector. The prepared modified catalysts were also investigated by an Apreo S LoVac instrument (FEI/ThermoFischer) coupled with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (AMETEK, Octane Elect Plus), operated at 2.0 for secondary electron imaging, and 25.0 kV for elemental analysis. The main properties of neat catalysts are summered in Table 1.

The Ni/ZSM-5, Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/CaO catalysts were in the form of fine powder with average diameter under 20 μm. Contrary, the Ni/Clinoptilolite catalyst has higher drain size. Another significant difference was found in the BET surface, because the Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst has 335 m²/g surface area, while the others less than 60 m²/g. Similar notable difference was reported regarding the “ S_{micro} ” value. It is important to mentioned, that Ni/ZSM-5 catalyst has the smallest average pore diameter, while Ni/Al₂O₃ has the highest. Regarding the C–C chemical bond scission effect of the catalysts, not only their surface area and Si/Al ratio, but also the acidity should be also a crucial property. The acidity follows the order of Ni/Al₂O₃ < Ni/CaO < Ni/ZSM-5 < Ni/Clinoptilolite. EDAX result well demonstrated, that due to the natural source of the clinoptilolite, it has 8.0% other elements (Fe, Ca, K, Na) in addition to those listed. It is also worth to mentioned, that the nickel content of the catalysts changes significantly, which could be explained by the difference surface properties of the applied supporters.

The desorption of ammonia is often used in order to determine the strength and amount of acid centres. The strength of the centres correlates with the desorption temperature. Since strongly bound probe molecules have high binding energies, increases temperatures are necessary to desorb these adsorbates [18]. The NH₃-TPD was carried out on four samples (fresh catalysts) under same condition. T_{max} values of TPD plots of ammonia desorbed from fresh catalysts decreases the in the following order: Ni/CaO > Ni/Al₂O₃ > Ni/Clinoptilolite > Ni/ZSM-5. However, the number of acid sites of fresh catalysts decreases as follows: Ni/Clinoptilolite > Ni/CaO ≈ Ni/ZSM-5 > Ni/Al₂O₃. However, it is important to be mentioned, that in case of CaO the ammonia TPD results are not concrete, due to the fact that CaO is a basic oxide. The high

Table 1

The morphological and acidic properties of fresh catalysts.

	Ni/ZSM-5	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	Ni/CaO	Ni/Clinoptilolite
Appearance	powdered	powdered	powdered	granulated (1,6–2,4 mm)
Si/Al	18.6	–	–	4.9
S_{BET} , m ² /g	335	0.6	55	18
S_{micro} , m ² /g	209	0	0	5
V, cm ³ /g	0.1178	0.0087	0.1673	0.0972
V_{micro} , cm ³ /g	0.0908	0	0	0.0022
D_{av} , nm	5.5	87	8.6	18.4
T_{max} NH ₃ -TPD, °C	155	220	308	170
Acidity, μmol/g	921	225	920	1953
O	59.3	45.4	32.2	48.9
Al	1.8	51.9	–	6.8
Si	34.9	–	–	33.1
Ca	–	–	58.6	1.4
Ni	4.0	2.7	9.2	1.9
Other	–	–	–	8.0

acidity of Ni/CaO can be explained by the measurement conditions. During the ammonia TPD, the number of the acidic sites are calculated by the consumed ammonia, which in case of CaO, resulted in the following chemical reaction:

Basically, the mentioned reaction requires higher temperatures (~500–700 °C), but owing to the nickel content, lower temperature was adequate (308 °C).

Fig. 1 shows the morphology of prepared catalysts impregnated with nickel. Based on their structure, rings and channels of the catalysts, their nickel content evolved differently. The CaO had the highest nickel content (9.2%) owing to its wide channel openings and active sites, while clinoptilolite had the smallest (1.9%) due to its lower surface area and pore volume. Besides, as it can be seen, the distribution of nickel is not unified, which also can be explained by the different pore sizes, average pore diameter of catalysts and the wet impregnation method. Afterwards, it is important to be mentioned, that the surface area of Ni/Al₂O₃ is significantly lower comparing the Al₂O₃, due to the impregnation, which could clogged its pores and covered the surface of catalyst.

2.3. Equipment

The experiments were carried out in a two zone tubular reactor (Fig. 2), aiming the in-situ carbon dioxide capture with increased synthesis gas yield. In the first reactor zone 5g of the raw material was placed, while 2.5g catalyst (Ni/ZSM-5, Ni/Al₂O₃, Ni/CaO, Ni/Clinoptilolite) was used in the second zone. Firstly, the temperature of the 1st reactor zone was determined, then that of the 2nd was investigated between 500 and 700 °C. Regarding the final temperature of the 2nd reactor zone, it was chosen with the consideration of the regeneration temperature. It is important to mention, that higher temperature than 800 °C for regeneration could cause structure deformation in case of catalysts. Afterwards the determination of the temperatures in the reactor zones, the regeneration cycles (during 10 cycles) of each catalyst was investigated for economic reasons. In case of preserving the

structure of catalysts and its decoking, the regeneration was carried out at 800 °C for 1 h. The measurements were performed under inert conditions (nitrogen flow, 42 ml/min), for 20 min. In order to capture the moisture of the gas silica gel, while for the gaseous product a Tedlar type gas bag was used, with only one sampling at the end of the measurement. At the end of the measurements, the product yield was calculated based on their weight balance (2).

$$100 - \frac{\text{Residue(g)} + \text{Generated water (g)}}{\text{Raw material (g)}} \cdot 100 = \text{Produced gas (\%)} \quad (2)$$

2.4. Product analysis

The composition of the gas products was investigated using a DANI type gas chromatograph equipped with a programed injector and a flame ionization detector. Rtx-1 PONA type 100 m long column with an internal diameter of 0.25 mm and film thickness of 0.5 μm was placed in the chromatograph. The analysis was performed at 35 °C isothermal condition. The detector and injector temperatures were 230 °C. The chromatograms were evaluated using Clarity software.

The hydrogen content of the gaseous products was also determined by gas chromatography using a DANI type gas chromatograph (with TCD detector) equipped with a CarboxenTM 1006 PLOT (30 m × 0.53 mm) column. During the experiments the following temperature program was used, the column space temperature at 30 °C for 18 min was kept, then it was raised to 120 °C with a heating rate of 15 °C/min, then the temperature was maintained at 120 °C for 2 min.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Raw material

To investigate the weight loss of raw material, a thermogravimetric analysis was performed by a Netzsch thermogravimetric analyser. During the measurement nitrogen atmosphere was used, with 20 °C/min heating rate until 800 °C. The arisen gases were analysed by a Bruker type FTIR connected to the TGA. The weight loss and dm/dt result of

Fig. 1. The prepared (a) Ni/ZSM-5 catalysts, (b) Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, (c) Ni/CaO catalysts, (d) Ni/Clinoptilolite catalysts.

Fig. 2. The schematic drawing of the equipment.

biomass raw material is shown in Fig. 3.

The decomposition of the raw material took place in several stages, resulting in a residue of 45.73%. As Fig. 1 shows, the degradation of the biomass took place in three main steps. Up to 135 °C, the physically bound moisture of the sample was removed (4.06%). The first decomposition step took place between 135 °C and 245 °C with a maximum of 225 °C. The weight loss rate was 6.36%. The second step was observed between 245 °C and 340 °C with a maximum of 325 °C, while the third decomposition step was observed between 325 °C and 405 °C. The last decomposition step was observed at a maximum of 405 °C. The weight loss of the sample was 19.62% in the second decomposition step and 15.11% in the third. In the first degradation step, mainly the lighter molecular weight volatiles was removed, while in case of the third the hemicellulose units started to degrade, while that of the second degradation step both the hemicellulose and cellulose units. At the last step, mainly the lignin units started to decompose, due to its phenolic polymer structure.

The TG-FTIR provides information about the functional groups of volatiles including non-condensable gases, (CO, CO₂, CH₄) and condensable volatiles (H₂O, methanol, acids, phenols) as a function of temperature. As it can be seen in Fig. 3, the raw material degraded as it was found during pyrolysis of lignocellulose materials [15]. The carbon monoxide mainly arises at low temperature (~350–450 °C) from the cracked ether and carbonyl groups, while at higher temperature (>600 °C), it can mainly be originated from the secondary reactions [15]. At low temperature carbon dioxide arises from hemicellulose, while that of at higher temperature from lignin units. The mentioned CO₂ peaks can be observed at 2356 cm⁻¹ and between 668 and 500 cm⁻¹. The different stretching and bonds were revealed in the first 1000 s, except the characteristic peaks of CO₂. Regarding the H₂O, the peaks are caused by the evaporation of moisture content and dehydroxylation of carbohydrates [15]. O–H stretching of H₂O between 4000 and 3468 cm⁻¹, while at 1645 cm⁻¹ H–O–H bending can be detected. The same conclusion can be noted regarding the C=O aldehyde and ketone stretching and C–O–C stretching which appeared at 1830–1650 cm⁻¹ and at 1100 cm⁻¹, respectively. Methane tetrahedral ν₄ vibration appeared at 1306 cm⁻¹ with low absorbance, while asymmetrical C–H bending and stretching can be observed at 1500 cm⁻¹, which can be originated from the lignin content. Over time, the mentioned groups cannot be detected excepting the characteristic peaks of CO₂.

Fig. 3. The weight loss, the dm/dT result and FTIR spectra of the raw material.

3.2. Determining the temperature in the 1st reactor zone

In order to get the appropriate temperatures during the experiments, preliminary experiments are needed. At first, the temperature of the 1st reactor zone should be chosen, considering the yields (Fig. 2). As Fig. 3 shows, with the increase of the temperature the yield of gas was escalated while that of the residue was decreased. Besides, in the range of 400–700 °C the yields was not significantly changed. That phenomenon can be explained by the degradation of the lignocellulosic units. As it is widely known, the biomass is built up from cellulose (40–60%), hemicellulose (15–30%) and lignin (10–25%), having different degradation temperature ranges regarding its component [19]. A significant difference cannot be remarked between 500 and 700 °C, however, at higher temperatures, the yield of gas was increased by 10.6% due to the decomposition of lignin units [19]. Nevertheless, during biomass degradation, water formation takes place, which in case of the mentioned experiments was under 1%. Based on the mentioned low value, the amount of water is not depicted on Fig. 4.

Regarding the gas products, as Fig. 5 depicts, with increasing temperature, the yield of hydrogen, carbon monoxide and methane was escalated mainly owing to the following reactions [20]:

Fig. 4. The yields during the determination of temperature in the 1st reactor zone.

Fig. 5. The determination of the temperature in the 1st reactor zone.

Besides, the amount of carbon dioxide and lighter hydrocarbons was decreased, due to the thermal cracking (3), the steam reforming (water has arisen from the moisture of biomass) (7) and dry reforming reactions (8) (carbon dioxide surplus from biomass, even at higher temperatures) [20]. Regarding the amount of carbon monoxide and lighter hydrocarbons, the raise of the temperature was not resulted in significant change, while that of hydrogen, methane and carbon dioxide was remarkable with 1.1–19%, 2.2–8.5% and 5.8–28.8%, respectively. Since our work is mainly focusing on the regeneration cycles of the used catalyst and its properties in carbon dioxide conversion, in the 1st reactor zone lower temperature, 400 °C was used in the following measurements, where the carbon dioxide yield is ~55%. Besides, the process has lower energy requirement, also, it can provide a possibility for further investigations on the effect of the temperature.

3.3. Determining the temperature in the 2nd reactor zone

After the determination of the temperature in the 1st reactor zone,

Fig. 6. The yields during the determination of temperature in the 2nd reactor zone.

the temperature of the 2nd was also investigated with and without catalysts between 500 and 700 °C (Fig. 2). As Fig. 6 depicts, the gas yield was increased by the enhanced temperature and with the presence of catalysts. However, it should be mentioned that the differences between the yields are lower than 5%, which can occur by the diverse particle size of raw material (<3 mm).

Also, it is important to note, that remarkable difference could not be observed among catalyst free and thermos-catalytic cases (only 1.2–7.5% of change). Besides the yield, the composition of the gas (Fig. 7) was also investigated in the presence of the four different catalysts. In the absence of catalyst the yield of hydrogen and carbon monoxide were increased by the escalated temperature in the 2nd reaction zone, while that of lighter hydrocarbons was decreased by 2.6%. Regarding the results, mainly the same tendency can be observed at all temperatures, while significantly the amount of the components changed.

Fig. 7 shows the change in the amounts of components compared to the non-catalytic measurement (Fig. 7(a)) at 500 °C (Fig. 7(b)), 600 °C (Fig. 7(c)) and 700 °C (Fig. 7(d)). In case of hydrogen, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide yield remarkable changes were observed at both temperatures. The hydrogen yield was increased by 0.3–6.9 mmol/g due to the higher temperature and the nickel content on the catalysts surface. In the presence of catalysts the carbon monoxide yields were enhanced by 3.8–13.8 mmol/g, which can be explained by the shifting in Boudouard reaction (4), water gas reaction (5) and reforming reaction (7). Latter can be observed with the lower methane and higher hydrogen yields in almost each case. Nevertheless, the mentioned Boudouard reaction (3) was only observed in the presence of catalysts, where coke deposition was appeared on its surface promoting the solid-gas reaction.

The effect of carbon dioxide capturing and decreasing was detected in case of Ni/Al₂O₃, Ni/CaO and Ni/Clinoptilolite with 0.3–23.7 mmol/g values. Based on the literature, in case of Ni/Al₂O₃ the reduction in the yield of CO₂ can be described with its specific surface area and crystallite size [21,22]. However, as it was mentioned before, during nickel impregnation, the specific surface area of the Al₂O₃ has decreased significantly, therefore, the CO₂ reduction besides the properties of alumina-oxide, was mainly occurred by the higher temperature and its Ni content which can also enhance the CO₂ adsorption capacity, as well as the adsorption activity. Besides, as it also can be mentioned in case of Ni/CaO, chemical adsorption can occur due to the hydroxyl and oxide groups on the surface resulting in carbonate or bicarbonate species [21, 22]. Regarding the Ni/Clinoptilolite, the high acidity can be mentioned

Fig. 7. The change in the amount of components compared to the no-catalyst points (a), during the determination of temperature in the 2nd reactor zone (b) at 500 °C, (c) at 600 °C, (d) at 700 °C.

which can evolve the CO₂ capturing effect, therefore CO₂ can be easily adsorbed owing to its beneficial properties (high quadruple moment) next to the hydrogen, methane and lighter hydrocarbons [23]. As Fig. 7 depicts the amount of the lighter hydrocarbons was decreased by 1.1 and 10.9 mmol/g, from which the highest value belongs to the Ni/ZSM-5 (8.1–10.9 mmol/g) owing to its high Si/Al ratio, its pore structure (narrow zig-zag pattern, limited diffusion) and better cracking function.

In terms of the generated syngas the presence of different catalysts were also investigated. As it can be seen in Fig. 8, with increasing temperature, the sum of hydrogen and carbon monoxide also increased. Besides, not only the nickel content on the catalyst surface but the carbon capturing/conversion had a positive effect as well as temperature on syngas yield. As it was mentioned before, the highest hydrogen yield (8.9 and 11.1 mmol/g respectively) was generated in the presence of Ni/

Fig. 8. The amount of synthesis gas during the determination of temperature in the 2nd reactor zone.

CaO and Ni/Clinoptilolite, while the highest carbon monoxide was obtained in the presence of Ni/Clinoptilolite. Referred to the results, Ni/Clinoptilolite provided the highest syngas yield at all temperatures (37.4, 38.6 and 48.3 mmol/g). Furthermore, it should be mentioned, that in syngas yield, compared to the non-catalytic points, a significant difference was observed (4.1–20.2 mmol/g). Based on the results, hereinafter 700 °C was used in the 2nd reactor zone, with 400 °C in the 1st reactor zone.

3.4. Regeneration cycles of catalysts

Fig. 9 shows the difference in the amount of each component compared to the first measurement point. As it is depicted, the amount of the lighter molecular weight hydrocarbons was increased by each catalyst in a wide range (0.7–11.4 mmol/g) from which Ni/ZSM-5 had the strongest influence in each regeneration cycle. This phenomena can be explained by coking and continuous pore clogging despite the regeneration cycles. Nevertheless, it should be mentioned that Ni/ZSM-5 and Ni/Al₂O₃ decreased the carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide amount with a significant value (0.5–8.1 and 4.5–11.8 mmol/g, respectively) as the cycles were progressed.

Regarding the Ni/CaO, the amount of carbon dioxide until the third regeneration cycle was decreased by 0.2–1 mmol/g, thereafter it was increased by 1.4–4.9 mmol/g. On the basis of earlier work, it can be explained by escalated specific surface area owing to the catalyst sintering effect caused by the severally used high temperature [26]. Besides, the amount of hydrogen and carbon monoxide was reduced by 2.1–7.1 mmol/g and 3.8–8.3 mmol/g, respectively. However, with the decreasing of hydrogen, the methane was increased by 0.1–2.3 mmol/g,

which can be explained by the methanation reaction (6). In the presence of Ni/Clinoptilolite the hydrogen and carbon dioxide content was decreased at each regeneration cycle by 1.0–7.1 mmol/g and 0.3–4.4 mmol/g, while carbon monoxide and methane content was increased (1.4–3.7 and 0.3–2.2 mmol/g). Concerning the amount of carbon monoxide, its value from the seventh regeneration cycle was significantly reduced by 4.5–9.2 mmol/g. The introduced phenomena can be explained by the favourable acidic properties of Clinoptilolite in carbon capturing, while the remarkable changes in composition from the seventh regeneration cycle may occurred by the coke deposition in the tetrahedral structure and on the surface of catalyst [23,24].

Fig. 10 shows the yield of the generated syngas at each regeneration cycle, where its yield was changed between the range 24.9–50.5 mmol/g. In the presence of Ni/ZSM-5, Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/CaO a slight decrease can be observed along with the regeneration cycles. However, in case of Ni/Clinoptilolite the synthesis gas yield was escalated until the sixth cycle (43–50.5 mmol/g), despite that it had the highest value from 7th–10th regeneration cycle compared with the used catalysts. Based on the results, it can be concluded, that the Ni/ZSM-5 and Ni/Al₂O₃ decreased the amount of carbon dioxide until the 5th regeneration cycle, while in case of Ni/CaO its value was reduced until the 3rd cycle. In the presence of Ni/Clinoptilolite the carbon dioxide content showed decreasing even at the last regeneration cycle. Due to the represented data, the Ni/Clinoptilolite resulted in the highest synthesis gas and the lowest carbon dioxide yield, while in case of Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/CaO the generated carbon dioxide has remained under 30 mmol/g for ten regeneration cycles.

3.5 Morphology of used catalysts.

Afterwards the regeneration cycles, the main properties of the

Fig. 9. The amount of components during the regeneration cycles, (a) Ni/ZSM-5, (b) Ni/Al₂O₃, (c) Ni/CaO, (d) Ni/Clinoptilolite.

Fig. 10. The amount of synthesis gas during the regeneration cycles.

catalysts was investigated, which are summarized in Table 2. During catalytic pyrolysis-gasification, the deactivation of catalysts strongly depends on the secondary reactions, as well as coke deposition. It should be mentioned, that through the thermochemical degradation of biomass oxygenates such as phenols, alcohols, ketones and aldehydes could formed, which are at higher temperatures and in the presence of catalysts start to decompose with the formation of coke. The generated coke clogs the pores and covers the specific surface area, causing activity decreasing. Therefore, the regeneration of catalysts is necessary.

As it can be seen the surface areas (except Ni/Al₂O₃) was decreased by the coke deposition, which caused clogging in the micropores of Ni/ZSM-5 and Ni/Clinoptilolite and pores at about 4 nm of Ni/CaO. Comparing the fresh catalysts (Section 2.2, Table 1), with the coked and regenerated ones, it can be said, that the highest and lowest decrease of S_{BET} values were observed for Ni/CaO coked (54%) and Ni/ZSM-5 coked (17%) respectively. Also, slight reduction was observed in the Si/Al ratio and V_{micro} in case of Ni/ZSM-5 and Ni/Clinoptilolite which can be explained by the partly blocked and inaccessible acidic centres. Besides, in case of Ni/CaO it can be mentioned, that the fresh catalyst did not have micropores, while that of the coked and regenerated were occurred, which also can be clarified with the increased average pore diameter values. This phenomenon can be explained with sintering effect which was caused by the numerous use at 700 °C, as well as with the several regeneration cycles at 800 °C. However, the mentioned effect was occurred until the 6th-7th regeneration cycles. In addition, the regeneration was considered effective due to the lower amount of coke deposition, which was removed almost totally in case of Ni/Al₂O₃, Ni/ZSM-5 and Ni/Clinoptilolite. Meanwhile no significant regeneration effect was observed after 10th cycle at 800 °C on surface area, pore volume, pore size distribution. The morphological parameters showed

almost the same values for “coked” and “regenerated” samples.

4. Conclusion

In this work, agricultural biomass was pyrolysed-gasified in a two-zone tubular reactor. As a catalyst, nickel impregnated ZSM-5, Al₂O₃, CaO and Clinoptilolite were used. The main aim was the reduction of carbon dioxide with the increase of syngas yield. During the measurements, not only the effect of the temperature and catalysts but the regeneration cycles of catalysts was investigated. At first, the temperature of the 1st and the 2nd reactor zone was determined, where 400 °C and 700 °C, while for the temperature of regeneration 800 °C was chosen. Regarding the 1st zone, in case of great amount of carbon dioxide production, as well as to investigate the CO₂ reduction and conversion effect of catalysts, low temperature was chosen. Besides, with the use of low temperature, the process is more energy efficient.

In case of all catalysts, the amount of lighter hydrocarbons was increased especially in the presence of Ni/ZSM-5 which was caused by coking and pore-clogging. In the presence of Ni/Al₂O₃ mostly the temperature had an effect on the product yield owing to the low S_{BET} surface of the catalyst which was mostly caused by the nickel impregnation. Regarding the Ni/CaO it can be mentioned, that due to the 10 regeneration cycles a sintering effect was noticed where a small amount of micropores was generated increasing the S_{BET} of Ni/CaO. Concerning the results obtained in the presence of Ni/Clinoptilolite, it can be mentioned that the highest synthesis gas yield was observed until the 6th regeneration cycle, due to its great quadrupole moment which helps in carbon dioxide capturing, with the increasing of carbon monoxide. Based on the results, it can be noted that the amount of carbon dioxide was decreased until the 5th and 3rd regeneration cycle (in case of Ni/

Table 2

The morphological properties of the used and regenerated catalysts after the 10th cycle.

	Ni/ZSM-5 coked	Ni/ZSM-5 regenerated	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ coked	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ regenerated	Ni/CaO coked	Ni/CaO regenerated	Ni/Clinoptilolite coked	Ni/Clinoptilolite regenerated
Si/Al	16.05	16.02	–	–	–	–	4.52	4.5
S_{BET} , m ² /g	279	288	2.1	2.1	19.4	44.7	14	13
S_{micro} , m ² /g	165	167	0	0	2.2	2.9	0.9	1.0
V_{micro} , m ³ /g	0.0765	0.0777	0	0	0.0009	0.0011	0.0003	0.0004
V, cm ³ /g	0.1191	0.1088	0.0209	0.0152	0.0943	0.1736	0.1028	0.0890
D_{av} , nm	5.7	4.9	66.5	54.3	10.2	14.6	21.3	20.0
Coke deposition, wt%	3.9	0.63	3.52	0.2	6.07	4.96	2.33	0.6

ZSM-5, Ni/CaO respectively), while with the presence of Ni/Clinoptilolite the decreasing can be observed even at the last regeneration cycle. Therefore, the Ni/ZSM-5, Ni/CaO can be used for 10 regeneration cycles with low activity change, however, not for syngas yield increasing in these measurement series.

Afterwards, it was stated, that the Ni/Clinoptilolite is suitable for CO₂ capturing with syngas yield enhancing for 10 regeneration cycles. However, in case of Ni/Clinoptilolite, longer regeneration cycles should be investigated in case of more information of activity changing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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